

Enigma Soccer Simulation 2D Team Description Paper 2024

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Abstract. This team description paper introduces Enigma’s team optimization directions and methods over the past year. One of our main focuses has been on refining move actions, including the implementation of formation press and chase techniques, to bolster our defensive and offensive strategies. The base code used by Enigma is agent2D[1].

Keywords: Soccer simulation 2D · RoboCup · AI.

1 Introduction

RoboCup, hosting robotic soccer competitions since 1997, aims to advance robotics research. The concept of robotic soccer emerged in 1992, The RoboCup competitions hold various leagues like rescue, soccer simulation, and standard platforms of soccer. The Soccer Simulation 2D (SS2D) League is a major one among them. SS2D is among the oldest. The "IranOpen", an annual competition since 2006, also aligns with this league. Team Xprogrammers was established in 2021 and joined the 2D soccer simulation starter league in IranOpen2022, securing the 7th place. Our team participated in IranOpen2023 SS2D starter league as well and took 8th place. Our team aimed to participate in RoboCup2023 however didn't participate due to complex issues. The name of our team has changed from "Xpro-grammers" to "Enigma" in 2024. The base code of our team changed from StarterAgent2D [2] to Agent2D. Enigma team aims to participate in the soccer simulation 2D major league for the first year. We tried to develop the base code built-in functions as well as add other ideas as new functions or conditions. We will be presenting some of our main changes which are improving our team's performance.

1.1 Related work

In the past few years there has been an improvement in many teams so here are some teams that we would like to be influenced by: Cyrus2022 has developed

an action called unmarking for escaping from opponent marking and finding a good spot for receiving a pass [3]. R3CESBU designed a new strategy with a Delaunay Triangulation algorithm, using Fedit2. R3CESBU changed the strategy pattern in Agent2d by designing a new strategy maker file and adding new formation configs[4]. Hades2D2023 divided the playing field into triangular for formation[5]. Hermes2D2023 has marked six rectangles along the field to enhance the formation efficiency[6]. Emperor2023 defense strategy makes it difficult for opponent to get near their goal by defining layers of protection, Each layer is responsible for doing certain jobs[7]. Namira2018 has developed a system called “Formation Detection” by creating 20 different formations with three and four layers[8]. Helios2022 has also been trying to adopt the strategy according to the specific opponent strategy [9]. Tehran2D improved defense by developing a block algorithm[10].

2 Formation

In the past few years there has been an improvement in many teams so here are some teams that we would like to be influenced by: Cyrus2022 has developed an action called unmarking for escaping from op-ponent marking and finding a good spot for receiving a pass [3]. R3CESBU designed a new strategy with a Delaunay Triangulation algorithm, using Fedit2. R3CESBU changed the strategy pattern in Agent2d by designing a new strategy maker file and adding new formation configs[4]. Hades2D2023 divided the playing field into triangular for formation[5]. Hermes2D2023 has marked six rectangles along the field to enhance the formation efficiency[6]. Emperor2023 defense strategy makes it difficult for opponent to get near their goal by defining layers of protection, Each layer is responsible for doing certain jobs[7]. Namira2018 has developed a system called “Formation Detection” by creating 20 different formations with three and four layers[8]. Helios2022 has also been trying to adopt the strategy according to the specific opponent strategy [9]. Tehran2D improved defense by developing a block algorithm[10](Fig 1).

Fig. 1. Spots are demonstrated as the center of each square

2.1 Play ON

different game modes may occur during a soccer simulation2D game having that considered it is necessary to set strategic formation for each game mode. While the game mode is “play on”, the distance between the ball and each spot is calculated and the player’s position will be changed according to the ball’s coordinate (Fig 2).

Fig. 2. Spots are demonstrated as the center of each square

2.2 Set Play

In game modes such as a corner, kick-in, free kick, etc. player’s position plays a significant role in taking over the ball. So in these game modes, a different position is a necessity. player’s position will be affected by the ball’s position(Fig 3).

Fig. 3. Two formation examples while the game mode is ‘kick in’

3 Press

We implemented a segmented approach with four distinct sections on the soccer field to optimize defensive actions. The field is divided into four segments by X-axis lines. These segments include the two sides near the goals and two divisions in the midfield. By dividing the field this way, different players can efficiently execute defensive strategies tailored to their respective areas. Our function, "Press", is pivotal to this defensive approach. It involves players strategically positioning themselves against the nearest opponent to disrupt their ball possession. This tactic dynamically unfolds across each segment, with specific players assigned to press in their designated areas. For instance, players 10 and 11 handle segment one, while players 7 and 8 focus on segment two, and so forth. This segmented pressing strategy not only enhances defensive capabilities but also serves as a potent offensive tool. It creates opportunities for goal-scoring while mitigating the risk of losing points. By preventing opponents from gaining possession, our team maintains a competitive superiority on the field.

4 Results

We intended to evaluate the effect of adding new functions on the team's progress. Yet our team needs a lot of improvements, and new behaviors will be added to our team until RoboCup2024. Identified areas for improvement are highlighted in the future work section. We measured our progress by running games between Enigma and base code (Table 1).

Table 1. The result by running games

Names	Enigma	Base
Goals	564	129
Avg goals	5.6	1.2

5 Future work

We aim to enhance player behavior, considering the impact of friction in shooting and passing scenarios. We plan to optimize strategies by utilizing reinforcement learning and neural networks for precise passing techniques. Drawing inspiration from top teams, we seek to predict opponents' movements, strategically unmark key players and adopt innovative concepts. Our multifaceted approach aims to advance both offensive and defensive strategies, keeping us at the forefront of competitive play. To achieve this, we're focused on improving player performance by addressing issues like friction, especially in shooting and passing. Our strategy

involves using reinforcement learning for pass strategies and neural networks to upgrade our formation. We're also exploring techniques used by other teams, such as predicting opponents' movements, unmarking key players, and enhancing passing skills for future use.

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